

Evaluation of Socio-Economic Status and Fishery Activities in Pyinbongyi Village, Bago Township

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Abstract

The study was conducted in Pyinbongyi Village, Bago Township to assess socio-economic status and fishery activities. There was 20 % of the households were randomly selected and interviewed in the study area. The results showed that average family size was 6 persons and 85.7 % of villagers were literate but 14.3 % were illiterate. There were many different livelihoods in the study area. The result showed that the main source of livelihood based on population was farmers that 15 % of villagers were farmers. The second and third highest livelihoods were cheroot maker and fishing which were represented 13.2 % and 6.5 % of villagers respectively. The result showed that 13.2 % of villagers especially many female were cheroot makers which was highest work force in the study area. There was 47.5 % of villagers were working in different kind of occupations and 52.5 % were students and dependents. Students and dependents were 16.5 % and 36 % of villagers respectively. The highest monthly income workers were mechanic/driver and shopkeeper that their monthly income was 600000 kyats, 450000 kyats respectively. The highest monthly income of livelihoods based on population was fishing and a fisher earned 270000.4 ± 7637 kyats while a farmer earned 210000 ± 6377.04 kyats. There was many different freshwater fish species distributed in the study area and collected fish species belong to 7 orders. Small scale fishers were observed although large scale fishers were not occurred and various types of fishing gears were used to catch fish for their families' consumption and income. Many people with low income in Pyinbongyi village fell in subsistence poverty. Job opportunities in dry season were higher than wet season especially in fishing. There was aquatic resources and rice were both fundamental to food security, nutrition and health particularly for poorer people. The fishers realized that fish catch rate was declining year by year that aquatic population were assumed to be decreasing in the study area. The study indicated that community base management and educational programme for local people were needed to preserve aquatic biodiversity.

Introduction

Myanmar, with a coast of 2826 km with many rivers flowing into the extended and large continental shelf of 213,720 km² with an Exclusive Economic Zone of 486000 km², is rich in natural fisheries resources. Inland freshwater bodies cover 8.1 million ha which 1.3 million ha are permanent, the remainder are seasonally inundated floodplain (Pedro, Smith, Silva, Tirendi, Funge-Smith, Haylor, Phillips and Chanratchakool, 2003).

Myanmar supports a diversity of freshwater ecosystem from fast-flowing mountain streams to wide, slow-flowing lowland rivers, as well as lakes and other non-flowing wetlands. Freshwater ecosystems in Myanmar support the livelihoods of significant proportion of the human population. As a result, they are frequently subjected to high levels of human use, often with negative implications for biodiversity.

The population of Myanmar is predominantly rural and a significant proportion lives below the US\$ 3 to 7 per day poverty threshold. Consequently, there are high levels of dependency on natural resources. The main direct threats to biodiversity in Myanmar are over exploitation and habitat degradation as well as habitat loss. The root causes of biodiversity loss

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in Myanmar include economic growth and increasing consumption, capacity constraints, lack of environmental safeguards, inadequate of grassroots support for conservation and global climate change (Leimgruber, Kelly, Streininger, Brunner, Miller and Songer, 2004). This study was conducted to assess socio- economic status, different kinds of fish species, various types of fishing gears, seasonal variation of fish species based on the catchments in the study area.

Materials and Methods

Pyinbongyi village is located in Bago Township, Bago Division was chosen as the study area. It is situated at 16° 45' N, 95° 34' E and 25 km far from Northern East of Bago, East of the Yangon to Mandalay highway. Moeyingyi Wildlife Sanctuary (Moeyingyi Wetland) lies in the North - East of Pyinbongyi village. It is one of the protected areas in Myanmar and the area is 100 square kilometer. The study was conducted from December 2017 to July 2018.

Fish specimens were collected and noted together with the types of fishing gears. Scaled photographs were taken soon after catch. Collected specimens were tagged and preserved in 10 percent formalin. Diagnostic characteristics of the collected specimens were studied following after Day (1978), Jayaram (1981), Talwar and Jhingran (1991). The abundance of fish species caught in the catch was randomly counted. The sampling frame was based on the list of households in the village. There was 20 % of the households were randomly selected from 1931 households to find out the information by using face to face interviews and direct observation.

The recorded data were tabulated and showed with graphs. Data were analyzed by paired sample “ T ” test in SPSS software to sort out the differences of monthly income of villagers in each income level between dry and wet season.

Results and Discussion

Population, age, races and religion

Pyinbongyi village has 1931 households with the population of 9267people. Female population was higher than male that 52.27% and 47.73% of villagers were female and male respectively in the study area. The average family size was 6 persons and minimum and maximum family size was 2 and 14 persons respectively. The result showed that family size of 89 % of total households was 2 to 8 persons (Table. 1).

Age groups were categorized in two groups and age groups of above 18 years and below 18 years were 68.23% and 31.77 % respectively (Fig1). It indicated that working age group was high in the village that was one of the advantages for rural development. Most of villagers were Myanmar and few villagers were Kayin, Mon and Rakhine ethnic groups. Buddhism was main religion in the study area.

Table 1. Family size of each household in Pyinbongyi village

Family size (person)	No:of households	Percent of total house holds
2	39	10.96
3	45	12.64
4	50	14.05
5	58	16.29
6	70	19.66
7	30	8.44
8	26	7.3
9	12	3.37
10	8	2.24
11	8	2.24
12	0	0
13	0	0
14	10	2.81
Total	356	100

Fig 1. Distribution of household members by age group

Educational status

There was a monastic school, primary school, and high school in Pyinbongyi village. The survey showed that 85.7 % of villagers were literate but 14.3 % were illiterate in the study area. There was literate male and female were 45.57 % and 54.42 % of villagers respectively. It was recorded that 77.5% of villagers studied in government schools and 8.2 % studied in monasteries. The study showed that 63 % of villagers who studied in government schools received primary, middle and high school level education and 35 % of villagers studied in primary schools only because many poor parents cannot afford their children to study in secondary school.

Therefore, many children drop out of school after primary school level. The poverty of most households necessitates that school children frequently work in agriculture, fishing and herding animals, a major factor in the low educational level of the population. There was 14.5 % of the villagers received university level education (Fig. 2). There was established a library in Pyinbongyi village and the people were favored to get more knowledge and information from the library. It was one of important roles for human resources development in this village.

Fig 2. Education level of the villagers in Pyinbongyi Village

Health

The public clinic was established in the village. According to the head of the clinic, sometimes outbreak waterborne diseases such as cholera, diarrhea and villagers who were needed to be treated in hospital usually go to the public hospitals in Waw and Bago. Most of households had dug wells and the remaining households obtained their domestic water from these owners and the wetland. It was believed that it would be the main source of drinking water in the study area. The result showed that 85.5 % of households had latrines, most of the pour-flush type which discharged via plastic pipes into the well which it is 1-2 m depth but 14.5 % of households did not have latrines. It indicated that health knowledge was still required in these particular villagers to prevent disease outbreak.

Livelihoods

Rural livelihoods throughout the study area depended on the use of a vast range of natural resources. These were predominantly wetland resources – including the cultivation of a wetland crop (rice), and the harvesting of aquatic animals, as well as collection of a wide range of wild aquatic plants. There were many different livelihoods in the study area. The result showed that the main source of livelihood based on population was farmers that 15 % of villagers were farmers. The second and third highest livelihoods were cheroot maker and fishing which were represented 13.2 % and 6.5 % of villagers respectively.

Other livelihoods were animal owner, government staff, mechanic, driver, cropper, astrologer, tailors, barber, logger, catching Bee- Lar (*Lethocerus americanus*) and collection of snail and wide range of wild aquatic plants such as water convolvulus, water hyacinth, water lily and arum plant for household consumption, animal feed and selling these plants for their income. The result showed that 13.2 % of villagers especially many female were cheroot makers which was highest work force in the study area. There was 47.5 % of villagers were working in different kind of occupations and 52.5 % were students and dependents. Students and dependents were 16.5 % and 36 % of villagers respectively (Fig 3). Few people especially young people migrate to metropolitan areas in search of non-farm jobs that it would be threaten to the village to be labour shortage in future.

Fig 3. Occupation of household members in Pinbongyi Village

Comparison of monthly income among livelihoods

In the study are, the highest monthly income workers were mechanic/driver and shopkeeper that their monthly income was 600000 kyats, 450000 kyats respectively. The highest monthly income of livelihoods based on population was fishing and a fisher earned 270000.4 ± 7637 kyats while a farmer earned 210000 ± 6377.04 kyats (Fig. 4). Most farmers were small scale farmers who owned with small farm. Cheroot makers were second highest population among villagers and they were represented 16.7 % of workers in the study area.

Fig 4. Average monthly income by different livelihoods in Pinbongyi Village

Comparison of monthly income of villagers between dry and wet season

Percent of the people who earned 120000, 350000, 400000, 450000 kyats per month were significantly different between dry and wet season ($P < 0.05$). The result showed that average monthly income of 57 % and 30 % of the people who were working, was less than 350000 kyats and 200000 kyats respectively and 18.5 % earned more than 350000 kyats during dry season. Many women and some students worked in farms for plantation or crop harvesting that they earned lower income which was less than 3000 kyats per day.

Catch rate in dry season was more than wet season and monthly income of fishers in dry season was higher than wet season. It was favoured to increase number of fishers during dry season. The result showed that monthly income less than 350000 kyats and 200000 kyats was

74.3 % and 45 % of the people respectively in wet season while 9.9 % earned more than 350000 kyats because fish catch rate in wet season was less than dry season. It indicated that they earned low income and many fishers shifted to another job as general workers in the field (Fig 5). It concluded more job opportunities and income of villagers were increased especially in fishing in dry season.

There was many villagers can utilize aquatic resources such as vegetables, aquatic animals and plants as well as other things they needed for their households consumption from the wetland. It indicated that they can collect some things in the wetland for their meal and their income could be used for other things they needed for their households. It was reflected many people with low income in Pynbongyi village fell in subsistence poverty, not absolute poverty.

Fig 5. Monthly income of villagers in dry and wet season

Gender

Women and girls played important role within the households and taking on domestic responsibilities. Women and children were involved in fishing, the post-harvest processing of fish and collection of aquatic resources in the study area. The result showed that 48.01 % of workers were female while 52.0 % of workers were male. There was 85 % of cheroot makers were female and 75 % of fishers were male in the study area (Table 2).

Table 2. Livelihoods of household members by sex in the study area

	Sex		Total(%)
	Male(%)	Female(%)	
Fisher	5.5	1.83	7.34
farmer	4.58	3.67	8.25
Shopkeeper	14.67	3.67	18.33
Animal owner	0.04	0.06	0.09
Mechanical	0.07	0	0.07
Driver	3.12	0.18	3.3
Cheroot maker	1.65	9.17	10.82
Astrologer	0.04	0	0.04
Tailor	0.04	0.52	0.55
Barber	0.09	0.09	0.18
dependent	1.83	4.58	6.42
Logger	0.07	0	0.07
student	20.3	24.24	44.54
Total	52	48.01	100

Composition of recorded fish species in the study area

Myanmar has many kind of fish species in inland and marine water. A total of 754 species that include 291 species in freshwater and 463 species in brackish as well as marine water is found in Myanmar (Fishbase, 1996). There was many different freshwater fish species distributed in the study area (Table 3). The result showed that the collected fish species belong to 7 orders; Perciformes, Siluriformes, Cypriniformes, Symbranchiformes, Osteoglossiformes, Beloniformes and Tetraodontiformes.

According to fishers, *Puntius chola*, *Amblypharyngodon mola*, *Esomus caudocellatus*, *Ophisternon bengalensis*, *Glossogobius giuris*, *Eleotris scintillars*, *Lates calcarifer*, *Tetraodon cutcutia*, were caught during rainy season. *Notopteus notopteus*, *Mystus menoda*, *Wallago attu*, *Clarias batrachus*, *Heteropneustes fossilis*, *Macroganathus aral*, *Parambassis ranga*, *Anabas testudineus*, *Channa striatus*, *Channa punctata*, *Channa gachua*, *Colisa labiosa* were caught the whole year (Table 4). It indicated that many fish species from different places were migrated out of the rivers to the wetland as spawning and nursery grounds during rainy season that fishers caught many different fish species in rainy season.

Table 3. Composition of recorded fish species in the selected area

No	Order	Family	Scientific Name	Common Name	Local Name
1	Osteoglossiformes	Notopteridae	<i>Notopteus notopteus</i>	Feather back	Nga-phe
2	Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	<i>Osteobrama belangeri</i> <i>Puntius chola</i> <i>Amblypharyngodon mola</i> <i>Esomus caudocellatus</i> <i>Labeo mandina</i> <i>Catla catla</i> <i>Rohtee cortio</i> <i>Labeo rohita</i>	Carplet Swamp barb Molar carplet Flying barb Carp Catla Carplet Rohu	Nga-phe-aung Nga-khone- ma Nga-bei- phyu Nga- maw- tawt Nga-ohn-done Nga-thaing Nga-phan-ma Nga-gyin-myat- san-ni
3	Siluriformes	Bagridae Siluridae Clariidae Heteropneustidae Schilbeidae	<i>Mystus seenghala</i> <i>Mystus pulcher</i> <i>Mystus menoda</i> <i>Ompok bimaculatus</i> <i>Wallago attu</i> <i>Clarias batrachus</i> <i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i> <i>Pseudeutropius atherinoides</i>	River catfish Pulcher mystus Menoda catfish Silvery cat fish Fresh water shank Catfish Sting catfish Schilbid catfish	Nga-jaung Nga-zin-yaing Nga-eike Nga-nu-than Nga-batt Nga-khu Nga-gyee Nga-than-jate
4	Beloniformes	Belonidae	<i>Xenotodon cancila</i>	Freshwater gar fish	Nga-phoung-yoe
5	Symbranchiformes	Sybranchidae Matacembelidae	<i>Monopterus bengalense</i> <i>Macroganathus aral</i> <i>M. zebrinus</i> <i>Mastacembelus armatus</i>	Mud eel Onestripe spiny eel Zebra spiny eel Tire track eel	Nga- shint Nga- mwei- doe Nga-mwei-doe -bae-jar Nga-mwei-nga-gar

No.	Scientific name	Jan	Feb	Mar	April	May	June	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
18.	<i>pseudeutropius atherinoides</i>		+	+	+	+							
19.	<i>Xenetodon cancila</i>		+	+	+	+							
20.	<i>Ophisternon bengalensis</i>		+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+			
21.	<i>Macroganathus aral</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
22.	<i>Macroganathus. zebrinus</i>		+	+	+	+							
23.	<i>Mastacembelus armatus</i>		+	+	+	+							
24.	<i>Parambassis ranga</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
25.	<i>Glossogobius giuris</i>						+	+	+	+			
26.	<i>Eleotris scintillars</i>						+	+	+	+			
27.	<i>Anabas testudineus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
28.	<i>Channa striatus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
29.	<i>Channa. punctata</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
30.	<i>Channa. gachua</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
31.	<i>Colisa labiosa</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
32.	<i>Lates calcarifer</i>						+	+	+	+			
33.	<i>Tetraodon cutcutia</i>						+	+	+	+	+	+	

Fishing gears used in the study area

There was 7.34 % of villagers were fishers and 1.83 % of total fishers were female. More fishing activities were found during dry season after water level was receded in dry season. All fishers were small scale fishers and used various types of fishing gears to catch fish for their families' consumption and income. In the study area, fishers caught aquatic animals by gill net, cast net, skimming net, fish trap, encircling gill net, prawn scoop net, seine net, bottom set gill net and long line trap, eel trap and bamboo trap in dry season.

Another fishing method in dry season was that fishers fixed many branches of trees in the water to create the refugee area of fish and other aquatic animals. Some fishers fed fish with rice bran or broken rice nearby these places to get more fish when they harvested fish. They usually harvest fish in these places during summer when fish price is increased. They confined around the branches by net to prevent fish escape from the branches after that they started to catch fish.

Bottom set gill net, prawn scoop net, long line trap, fish trap and eel trap were used in wet season and catch rate in wet season was lesser than dry season. Fishery activities supported not only domestic consumption but also income by selling fish they caught in the village and fish were shipped as fresh or frozen fish from the depots to the markets in Waw, Bago and Yangon.

Aquatic resources utilization in the study area

The study observed that aquatic resources and rice were both fundamental to food security, nutrition and health particularly for poorer people. As the main animal protein source, aquatic resources are vital to maintaining people health and well-being (Richard, Eric and Simon, 2004). Fish, commonly small fresh fish, dried fish, fish paste and fermented fish products were observed to exceed other animal protein sources such as meat in the study area.

Many different aquatic species were distributed in the study area. According to fishers that fisher population were gradually increasing and daily catch rate was decreasing year by year that aquatic population were assumed to be declining in the wild. The suitable ways intended to sustain aquatic resources in the study area are (1) There should be controlled fishing activities although fishing was not allowed in this protected area. The real constraint was that there was difficult to control fishing activities by patrolling and guarding in very wide area (100 square kilometer) of the wetland because of limited budget. Therefore, controlling fishing activities was not practical by doing patrolling and guarding. On the other hand, many people were poor and they depended on aquatic resources in the wetland to survive their life. Fishers caught fish and other aquatic animals there even they know this area was banned for fishing because of their households' income.

Government enforcement was essential to be balance between sustainable aquatic resources and people livelihood in the study area. There was needed to organize fishers and villagers to participate in sustainable aquatic resource management program led by government and Non Government Organizations (NGOs) in the study area. Mekong River Commission (1999) described that wetland fisheries development is mainly needed community base management that it should be organized the rural people especially fishers to participate it. They are key participant to success it. (2) It was required to create job opportunities and new livelihood or increase income of existing other livelihoods that some fishers would be persuaded to change to new livelihood if income of new livelihood was higher than their income. It was effected to reduce fisher population and favoured to decrease aquatic resources utilization. (3) Stocking of indigenous fish, prawn and other aquatic seed to increase aquatic population in the wetland. New species should not be stocked in the wetland that would disturb the indigenous species' habitat, production and spread disease. (4) There were many paddy farms in the study area and these farms should be converted to the farm with rice fish culture system to increase fish production, household income and consumption as well as decrease utilization of aquatic resources in the wetland. These ways were not only saved aquatic population but also created job opportunities and better income in the study area.

Conclusion

The study showed that the working age group in the village was very high that was one of the advantages for rural development. Literacy rate was high but health knowledge was still required in the village especially the villagers who did not have latrines to prevent disease outbreak. Women and girls played important role within the households and sex ratio of workers was approximately equal. Women were involved in fishing, post harvest processing of fish and collecting of aquatic resources. Farmers were small scale farmers with small farm which most farms was grown paddy.

The main source of livelihood based on population was fishing and farming with highest income and nearly half of the population worked in different livelihoods. More fishing activities were found during dry season. The study indicated job opportunities in dry season

were higher than wet season especially in fishing. This study showed that many people who earn with low income in Pyinbongyi village fell in subsistence poverty, not absolute poverty.

There was many different freshwater fish species were recorded. All fishers were small scale fishers and used various types of fishing gears to catch fish for their household's consumption and income. The fishers realized that fish catch rate was declining year by year because fishers population were gradually increasing that high fishing pressures and high demand of fish consumption by increasing population density were favoured to be over exploitation of aquatic resources and threaten to aquatic biodiversity in the study area. The study indicated that community base management and educational programme for local people were needed to preserve aquatic biodiversity. Further studies are needed to explore possible ways to meet improving food security through sustainable natural resources management and alleviate rural poverty in the study area.

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